

SensApp

D5.3 Report on sensitivity and specificity for P-tau

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1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses the attention on the results achieved by DSS technology on the P-tau target protein. Analogously to the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2, it is important to note that since the protocol steps for all of the three target proteins of this project (A β 1-42; Tau; p-Tau) were performed fully manually in CNR labs (due to the lack of the automation system from Ginolis) we spent more time than expected for testing the protocol steps and for achieving a reasonable standardization and a reasonable background level, especially crucial when working at low concentrations. Therefore, the time available for the calibration tests and for the tests in body fluids was highly limited also in case of the P-tau target. This deliverable has a public dissemination level and therefore sensitive data not yet exploited in scientific publications and/or patents are not disclosed here in agreement with the Art.27 of the GA.

2. Samples and results

The biomarker investigated in this deliverable is the phospho-tau protein (P-tau). Unlike the case of the biomarkers A β 1-42 and Tau investigated in the Tasks 5.1 and 5.2, where the proteins were bought in pure form and hence diluted first in distilled water and then in body fluids for DSS tests, here it was possible to test the P-tau only retrieved from the Innotech kit of Fujirebio (ref 81575). The P-tau samples were available only in pre-determined vials with partially un-known solvent matrix (details not disclosed by the supplier). Therefore, the tests in pure reference samples were not possible and we directly tested the accumulation of droplets by DSS by using the as-received samples. The image below shows the typical side view recorded during DSS of such samples. During the accumulation of successive droplets, a non-negligible volume of a solid-like structure starts to grow on the surface of the glass slide, presumably produced by an excess of salt precipitation.

Typical side view image of the droplet accumulation by DSS in case of P-tau samples from the Fujirebio Innotech kit (ref 81575).

Anyway, after completing the droplet accumulation by DSS we performed the protocol steps in case of as-received samples of P-tau at 1059.7 pg/mL and 249.1 pg/mL from the kit mentioned above. Analogously to the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 we used here the glass slides functionalized with amine groups from PolyAn supplier (Berlin). The figure below shows schematically the electrostatic interaction between the biochemical species and the surface of the amine functionalized slides.

Amine Surfaces

for non-covalent coupling of negatively charged biochemical species via electrostatic adsorption

Schematic view of the electrostatic interaction between the biochemical species and the surface of the amine functionalized slide provided by PolyAn supplier (Berlin).

After DSS spots the amine slide was incubated in a humid chamber for 2 h at 25°C. For saturating excess protein-binding sites, the slide was covered with 2mL of blocking solution for 1 h at 25 °C. The blocking solution was used to dilute the antibody solutions. Then the slide was washed by placing it in a Petri dish with 10 mL of PBS 1X (Gibco 10010023) for 2 min. This washing cycle (WC) was repeated three times. A solution of primary antibody, 2 mL of Phospho-tau (Thr 181) (D9F4G) rabbit mAb (CellSignaling Technologies 12885) at the dilution of 1:200 was deposited on the slide and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The three WCs were repeated. Finally, the secondary antibody solution (ThermoFisher Scientific anti-Rabbit I A32733), at the concentration of 0.5 µg/mL, was incubated 1 h at 25 °C and the WCs were repeated. The fluorescence signal-to-noise ratio achieved for the spots at the end of the immunoreaction protocol was not satisfactorily. We believe that the solid-like structure mentioned previously may interfere with the immunoreaction process reducing dramatically the binding efficiency in both protein-slide and antibody-protein reaction. Additional efforts and investigation are required in a future research project to test alternative immunoreaction protocols and mixing buffers for reducing the impact of the solid accumulation.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the DSS module has been demonstrated to be successful in detecting the A β 1-42 and Tau biomarkers down to sub-picogram levels with a satisfactorily range of linearity (see D5.1 and D5.2). The deliverable D5.1 describes also the encouraging results achieved in the tests with body fluids using the biomarker A β 1-42 and the secondary labelled antibody as fluorescent probe. In addition, the comparative study performed with a commercial piezo-based biospotter (see D4.2) represents a benchmarking exercise which demonstrates the ability of DSS technology to concentrate biomolecules in tiny droplets in a reliable manner.

The limited time available for the tests with P-tau and the lack of commercial P-tau in pure form prevented us to perform a reproducible immunoreaction protocol after spotting through DSS technology, also considering the additional issue of the excess of salts. We believe that this P-tau biomarker deserves additional efforts and investigation to reduce the dramatic impact of salt precipitation by testing pre-treatments of the samples and alternative protocol procedures which could reduce the impact of non-specific binding (e.g. labelled primary antibody). The DSS module will need in future the integration with an automated liquid handling system for the immunoreaction steps following the DSS process, to significantly reduce the impact of the background level.